

POLICY BRIEF Plastic Additives

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Summary

Plastic additives are substances added to plastic material to improve its properties and enhance the manufacturing process. All plastic objects contain additives in amounts of a few units in weight percentage. Although useful, throughout the life cycle of plastic material, these additives may be released into the environment, with the potential to disrupt ecosystems and enter the human food chain. The complex and diverse chemical nature of plastic additives makes it difficult to regulate them and the lack of comprehensive environmental data hinders accurate risk assessments. There is a need to ensure these additives are chemically safe for humans and the environment, as well as to improve regulations and public awareness, encouraging responsible consumption.

Description of the Problem

Plastic additives encompass a plethora of substances with diverse functions in the plastic industry. They provide essential improvements to the physical and chemical properties of the material, like flexibility and colour, increase the resistance to fire, light and high temperatures, and can improve the manufacturing process by reducing costs.

Source: Modified from UNEP (2023)

However, some chemicals used as plastic additives, such as trace metals or phthalates, have been already restricted from many applications due to their toxicity, and others like bisphenols or benzophenones raise increasing concern due to their potential to disrupt the normal functioning of hormones.

UNEP has recently brought to focus the issue of chemical additives¹. More than 13,000 chemicals are associated with plastics and plastic production across a wide range of applications, of which over 3,200 additives, processing aids and non-intentionally added substances are of potential concern due to their hazardous properties.

Plastic goes through a life cycle, starting with the extraction of raw materials and ending with its recovery, reuse, recycling, or final disposal. Additives are not chemically bonded to the polymer and throughout this cycle, can migrate from the plastic to its surroundings, be it food, water, or soil. Migration can be engineered, and sometimes beneficial, but its unintended occurrence can result in harmful exposure, and its extent depends on the characteristics of the plastic material, the chemical in question and environmental conditions.

Most of the plastics are still incinerated and/or disposed of in landfills or dumpsites, the EU policies prompted an increase in recycling (e.g. carrier bags, drinking bottles).

Chemical additives hinder recycling as an end-of-life alternative. An example is the case of Brominated Flame Retardants (BFRs), recognized endocrine disruptors, which have been incorporated into recycled products, making recyclers face difficulties in ensuring the precise composition of secondary materials, which constrains the recycling process.

The composition of a plastic product in terms of additives is unknown even for the manufacturer, due to limited disclosure by original producers, the addition of multiple chemicals during different steps of the plastic item production, and the complex composition of many current plastic products such as copolymers, heteropolymers, or multilayers. Assessing the quantities and types of additives present in a plastic item by chemical analyses is extremely difficult and expensive due to the complexity and diversity in the chemical nature of additives and thus in the required analytical techniques. Therefore, the information on the qualitative composition of any commercialized plastic should be compulsory to allow consumers to make informed decisions and improve end-of-life management and circularity. Similarly, the complex chemical nature of additives and thus their environmental behaviour and effects towards biota remains poorly understood.

Data on the leachability and ecotoxicity of additives in the environment is limited and inconsistent, thus their impact is yet to be fully explored and progress is needed to standardise toxicity testing methods.

Policy Challenges

- **Limited Knowledge of Plastic Composition:** Plastic composition is not disclosed due to intellectual property agreements. The EU still lacks a comprehensive information base on all substances. Polymers are not subject to registration under REACH and information on low and medium-tonnage substances under REACH does not fully allow to identify critical hazard properties.
- **Inadequate Real-World Testing:** The standard's laboratory testing methods fail to accurately replicate real-world conditions, potentially leading to misleading conclusions. Different aspects such as the complexity of the polymer matrix, migration and release mechanisms, analytical limitations and presence of Non-Intentionally Added Substances (NIAS) should be considered.
- **Insufficient Evaluation of Additive Toxicity:** The current assessments are insufficient to ensure the additives are harmless to real-world ecosystems and the wildlife they support. There is an absence of restrictions on constituents like trace metals or substances of very high concern (SVHCs).
- **Limited Environmental Scope:** There is a necessity for comprehensive testing across diverse ecosystems (open-air, terrestrial, freshwater and marine environments, landfills, and ecosystems under anaerobic conditions) to prevent and identify adverse environmental impacts.

Relevance to Legislation

- Circular Economy Action Plan. Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
- Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability “Human biomonitoring studies in the EU point to a growing number of different hazardous chemicals in human blood and body tissue, including certain pesticides, biocides, pharmaceuticals, heavy metals, plasticisers and flame retardants”
- Global Action on Plastics
- Packaging Waste (Law and Publications tabs) – Revision of the Packing and Packaging Waste Directive
- Microplastics (Waste Framework Directive)
- Single-Use Plastics Directive
- RoHS Directive (Restriction of Hazardous Substances in Electrical and Electronic Equipment)
- The Stockholm Convention
- Guidelines of the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA)

Policy Recommendations

- **Encourage Comprehensive Real-World Testing:** Toxicity testing methods must be expanded to consider the full food chain in each ecosystem compartment and shall also focus on the bioavailability of contaminants to more accurately evaluate their ecotoxicological impacts
- **Establish Rigorous Additive Safety Assessments:** Require thorough evaluations of all additives used in plastics to confirm their safety for all ecosystems, including assessments for substances like trace metals and SVHCs. Compostable plastics, currently promoted for agricultural use, are designed to remain in the soil, as seen with certain mulch films. Therefore, requirements ensuring the absence of environmental toxicity to all components of biological communities in both aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems should be reinforced.
- **Expand Environmental Considerations:** Develop standards that encompass a broader range of environments, including freshwater, marine, landfill, and anaerobic settings, to address the full spectrum of potential plastic pollution impacts. Studies should focus on the bioavailability of the contaminants and not only on their occurrence in the environment, to determine their ecotoxicological impacts more accurately.
- **Prioritize Reduction and Systemic Change:** Emphasize reducing plastic usage and implementing systemic changes to transition towards a circular economy. Strengthen extended producer responsibility (EPR) programs to ensure manufacturers take accountability for the additives used in their products. Regulatory actions should ensure compliance across the plastic supply chain including the safety of imported plastic products in the EU.
- **Promote Behavioural Change from manufacturers to consumers:** Encourage industries to adopt the digital product passports (DPP), eco-labelling and certification schemes to provide accessible and comprehensive information that fully discloses the product's chemical content. Increase funding for research and encourage collaboration between industry and scientists to develop safer, environmentally friendly alternatives to hazardous additives. Decisions on alternative additives should use a priori Environmental and Human Health Risk Assessments to prioritize safety.
- **Enhance Public Awareness and Promote Responsible Consumption of Plastic Additives:** Improve public understanding of the issues surrounding plastic additives and encourage responsible consumption choices through education and awareness campaigns.

Anatomy of plastics

MONOMERS AND POLYMERS

Constitute main building blocks of plastic material

ADDITIVES

Bring desired functionality to the plastic material

OTHER INTENTIONALLY ADDED SUBSTANCES

Such as starting materials and catalysts

NON-INTENTIONALLY ADDED SUBSTANCES

Such as solvents, cleaning agents, or impurities from manufacturing or recycling

BREAKDOWN

Most widely produced plastics additives

Plasticizers

To make plastic softer and flexible

Fillers

That occupy space without changing functional properties

Flame retardants

To reduce flammability and prevent spread of fire

Other

Including colorants, antioxidants, heat and light stabilizers, lubricants, biocides or antistatic agents

Source: Modified from UNEP (2023)

Sources

- 1 UNEP (2023). Chemicals in plastics: a technical report. Geneva, Switzerland: United Nations Environment Programme and Secretariat of the Basel, Rotterdam and Stockholm Conventions. 144 p.

Interactive version

<https://labplas.eu/learning-hub/>

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